

USING AUTHENTIC MATERIAL AND CREATED MATERIAL FOR ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING. BENEFITS AND LIMITATIONS

Eshboltayeva Lola Baxtiyorovna

Termiz university of economics and service
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Abstract

This research describes authentic materials and created materials (teacher-made materials) especially their benefits and limitations in English Language Teaching (ELT). This research is library research. The researcher collects data from books and articles published in journals related to authentic material and created material. The analysis shows considerations in English Language Teaching (ELT) are whether to use authentic or created material. Authentic materials refer to manuscripts, photos, videos, and other sources that are not prepared specifically for educational purposes. Meanwhile, created materials refer to textbooks or others specifically developed as teaching materials. In practice, two methods for teachers/lecturers use teaching materials such as adapting and adopting. Any course books or commercial textbooks can be utilized to be adapted as created materials. Authentic materials from a variety of sources that incorporate real language use also can be adopted.

Keywords: Authentic material, created material, teacher-made material, English material, English Language Teaching (ELT).

INTRODUCTION

Teaching materials are major elements in assisting teachers in achieving better teaching and students' desired learning results (Tonawanik & Donavanik, 2019). Teachers can communicate new knowledge and language objects methodically and purposefully using properly chosen resources. Teaching materials are a type or group of learning substances designed to aid teachers/instructors in teaching and learning activities that are systematically organized to satisfy the required competence criteria. Teaching materials are information, tools, and texts required for planning and reviewing the implementation of learning and to assist in teaching and learning activities in the classroom. Teaching materials are arranged systematically to display a comprehensive list of competencies that students will master during the learning process. The importance of teaching materials in all teaching and learning activities necessitates their preparation so that the implementation of learning can accomplish objectives based on competence standards and core competencies. Relevance, consistency, and adequacy are the selection criteria for instructional materials. Relevance implies that learning materials are tied to competence standards and fundamental competencies. The idea entails that learning materials and fundamental skills that students must acquire are consistent. For instance, if four types of core skills must be mastered by students, then four types of subject matter must be taught. The notion of the appropriateness of the information being taught is adequate to aid students in mastering the fundamental competencies being taught. The amount of material should be neither too little nor too much. If insufficient, meeting competency norms and fundamental competencies will be hampered. However, learning too much of it would be an unneeded waste of time and effort.

Methods

Teaching materials play a crucial role in the learning process (Fitria, 2022d). The stance represents the teacher's explanation spoken in front of the class. The instructor must

communicate, and the information the instructor must provide is compiled in the instructional materials. Thus, teachers will be able to decrease the number of activities required to give the lesson. In the classroom, the instructor will have ample time to instruct or lead pupils' learning. On the other side, instructional materials are also positioned as instruments or means for attaining competence criteria and fundamental skills. Therefore, the development of instructional materials should be directed by competence criteria and fundamental skills. Teaching materials are also a student service provided by the education unit. Individualized assistance is possible with instructional materials. Learners (students) interact with authored content. It focuses on consistent (principles) data. Participants with a high rate of learning will be able to maximize their talents via the study of instructional materials. Slow learners will have the opportunity to review the educational materials many times. Thus, learning services for students may be optimized through the use of instructional materials. The existence of instructional materials has at least three significant positions. As a representation of the teacher's presentation, as a method of fulfilling competence requirements and fundamental skills, and as a way of improving student services are the three roles. Identifying the type of material is done so that the compilers of teaching materials are carried out so that the types of material that will be presented can be recognized correctly. The identification results are then mapped and organized according to the chosen approach (procedural or hierarchical). Thus, the compilers of teaching materials will easily take the next step, namely determining the form of presentation. The form of presentation can be chosen according to needs such as textbooks, modules, dictation, information sheets, or simply teaching materials. If the form of presentation has been determined, the compilers of the teaching materials develop a structure or presentation framework. The frameworks are filled with predefined material. This activity includes drafting (discussing, making illustrations, drawings) teaching materials. The draft was later revised. The results of the revision were tried out, then revised again, and then finalized. Furthermore, teachers have been able to use these teaching materials to teach their students. Teaching materials are a key component of a language program. Whether teachers use textbooks or not, institutional materials are usually provided as a basis for learners and language practice in the classroom. For inexperienced teachers, learning materials can be an exercise, as they provide ideas on how to plan and teach according to the format. They need: (1) Printed materials, such as books, notebooks, worksheets, or reading books (Fitria, 2022b). (2) Non-printed materials, such as cassettes or audio, video, or computer-based materials. (3) The combination of printed and non-printed materials, such as materials that can be accessed by the internet. In addition, materials that are not designed for learning, such as magazines, newspapers, and TV. Today, EFL teachers have a lot of choices in terms of teaching methods and materials (Kirana, 2016). Some considerations that teachers should pay attention to while employing materials are as follows: teachers should offer clear instructions to students, teachers should be more creative in generating resources for students, and teachers should expand their understanding of developing resources for students with special needs because each student has unique features, resources should be implemented based on the student's capability and ability (Prabajati, 2015). Cunningsworth (1995) states the role of materials in language learning (especially textbooks), namely (a) resources in presenting material, (b) sources of activity for students in interactive practice and communication, (c) reference sources for

students in grammar, vocabulary, and so on, (d) sources of incentives and ideas in-class activities, (e) syllabus, where teachers reflect on the learning objectives that have been set, and (f) assistance for teachers who are inexperienced and lack confidence. Teachers may use teaching materials as the main source of learning. The materials provide a basis for course content, a balance of teaching skills, and a variety of student language practices. Most English teaching programs include teaching materials. Teachers rely heavily on a varied range of materials to assist their teaching and students' learning, including textbooks, videotapes, and photographs, as well as the Internet (Howard & Major, 2004). Meskill (2002) states that instructional tool is treated as 'material'. The teaching material can be categorized into three types include: 1) Authentic material (pre-existing material generated for purposes other than language instruction). Authentic materials can also be thought of as "found" materials. Visuals from the target culture, posters, brochures, postcards, menus, etc. are standard fare in the classroom.; 2) Commercially produced material (items manufactured by publishers that are meant expressly for language instruction such as textbooks); and 3) created/handmade (teacher/student-produced) materials. The results of created materials make for a more tailored approach to teaching a particular group of learners.

Conclusion

Collecting, selecting, and matching authentic materials with specific lessons can take more time (Gebhard, 2006). Therefore, EFL teachers need to allocate more time to prepare the materials to go with specific lessons. This is the difficulty for EFL teachers who desire to improve their students' language skills by offering realistic resources for lessons. Another limitation is that authentic materials may have complex language or dictions that students find difficult to understand. Students with a low degree of proficiency sometimes struggle to grasp the information. According to Richards (2001), authentic materials frequently contain difficult language, unnecessary vocabulary items, and complicated language structures, which places a strain on the instructor in lower-level classrooms. To avoid this, teachers should carefully select the most appropriate genuine resources for their students based on their level of ability. Teachers must also pay close attention to the difficulty of vocabulary and the organization of real materials to avoid a large gap between the contents and the learners' competency. Lower-level students should be supported by suitable assignments when utilizing authentic resources since challenging content may discourage and confuse low level students due to a lack of vocabulary and structures utilized in the target language.

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